

NEVEN JOVANOVIĆ

Marko Marulić, Renaissance lexicons
and architectural Latin

To be able to write about a field of knowledge clearly and effectively, an author must use proper words in a proper way. When Renaissance authors wrote in Latin about architecture – even when, and especially when, they themselves were not architectural experts and when architecture was not their main theme – which words did they choose, how did they use them, and how have they learned them? I will show what we can find out about these matters on the example of Marko Marulić (1450–1524) from Split.¹

¹ This paper is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and innovation programme (GA n. 865863 ERC-AdriArchCult): Architectural culture of the early modern Eastern Adriatic, AdriArchCult. – Groundwork study of Marulić and Renaissance lexicography (with different material) is J. RAMMINGER, *The role of Classical, Medieval and Renaissance lexicography in the development of Neo-Latin: some examples from Latin works of Marcus Marulus*, in: «Studi umanistici piceni» 31 (2011), p. 75-86. Accessible general surveys of Marulić: L. BORSETTO (edited by), *Italia-Slavia tra Quattro e Cinquecento. Marko Marulić umanista croato nel contesto storico-letterario dell'Italia e di Padova*, Atti della Giornata di studio,

Padova, 7 dicembre 2001, Alessandria, Edizioni dell'Orso, 2004; B. LUČIN (edited by), *The Marulić reader*, Split-Long Island City, Književni krug Marulianum - Hrvatski svjetski kongres, 2007; Id., *Iter Marulianum. Da Spalato a Venezia sulle tracce di Marko Marulić*, Rome, Viella, 2008; F. POSSET, "Marulus, Marcus", in: F. W. BAUTZ (edited by), *Biographisch-bibliographisches Kirchenlexikon*, vol. XXXII, supplement XIX, Nordhausen, Verlag Bautz, 2011, p. 942-947. «Colloquia Maruliana», an annual publication devoted to Marulić and Croatian Renaissance humanism, is freely accessible online, at: <<https://hrcak.srce.hr/index.php/colloquia-maruliana>> (p. consulted on 10 september 2024).

1. Marko Marulić

In the 16th and 17th century Marulić, as Marcus Marulus Spalatensis, achieved certain fame with his two religious compilations – *De institutione bene vivendi per exempla sanctorum* (first attested edition Venice, Franciscus Lucensis de Consortibus et Bernardinus de Vitalibus, 1507) and *Euangelistarium* (first attested edition Venice, Melchiorre Sessa the Elder, 1516). We know that Marulić's humanist interests ranged widely: in 1490-1510 he added a commentary to the poems of Catullus in the manuscript codex which is also our only extant source for Petronius' *Cena Trimalchionis*;² he wrote poetry in Latin, Croatian and Italian; translated from Croatian and Italian into Latin; put together a very early manuscript collection of commented ancient inscriptions, *In epigrammata priscorum commentarius* (1503-1510). Marulić, however, did not travel much outside his Dalmatian place of birth (he visited Venice and perhaps Padova, and went to Rome in 1500 on a Jubilee pilgrimage). His importance remains primarily local: in 1501, he composed the first authorial epic poem in Croatian, the *Judita* (first printed in Venice, Guilielmo da Fontaneto de Monteferrato, 1521); the poem ensured its author pride of place in the canon of Croatian literary history.

For our investigation, Marulić is a perfect representative of the humanist majority: well educated and well-read, a master of language and literature, but surely not among the best known or best-connected authors of his time; up-to-date in his interests, but removed from the main cultural centers; sharing the Italian culture, but himself not Italian.

A reconstruction of Marulić's lexicographical horizon is made easier by the fact that we have good insight into the resources at Marulić's disposal: his will and associated documents include two lists of books in his library (some of the books survive to this day, with Marulić's marginal notes)³ and we have a large number of Marulić's own works, some of which were neither published nor intended for publication in his lifetime.

² The *codex* is today in PARIS, Bibliothèque nationale de France, *Par. lat. 7989*. On Marulić and *Par. lat. 7989* see (with summaries in English) B. LUČIN, *Marulićeva ruka na trogirskom kodeksu Petronija* (Codex Parisiensis *Lat. 7989* olim *Traguriensis*), in: «Colloquia Maruliana» XIV

(2005), p. 315-320; ID., *Marul, Katul i Trogirski kodeks Petronija* (Codex Parisiensis *Lat. 7989* olim *Traguriensis*), in: «Colloquia Maruliana» XVI (2007), p. 5-44.

³ A. ZANINOVIĆ, "Marulićeve knjige u Dominikanskoj knjižnici u Splitu", in: *Zbornik u proslavu petstogodišnjice rođenja*

2. Investigation and hypotheses

From Marulić's Latin opus I have selected two passages in which architectural terms are prominent; then I found out whether and how some of these terms were described in lexicographical literature – lexicographical sometimes more in its function than in its form – of Marulić's time. I concentrated on works that we know Marulić possessed in his library or used in his writings, but I have taken into account some other titles as well. The hypotheses were: 1. there existed, between the Renaissance authors and the ancient sources of architectural terms (such as Pliny and Vitruvius), lexicographical intermediaries; 2. these lexicographical intermediaries influenced the Renaissance humanist usage.

I will consider the following passages from Marulić's works: a short interpretation of the allegorical meaning of columns in the Temple of Jerusalem from the *De institutione bene vivendi per exempla sanctorum* and a description of the biblical King David's palace from the epic poem *Davidiad* (1510-1517).⁴ The architectural terms which I will follow in Marulić's possible sources and contemporary lexicographical literature are seven; in alphabetical order: *asarotum*, *clatratus*, *crustatus*, *epistylum*, *lapillus*, *ophites*, *testudineus*.

3. Lexicographic sources in Marulić's library

Of the two testamentary lists of Marulić's books, the first one (titled *Repertorium librorum*) was drawn up before 1521 by Marulić himself, as an

Marka Marulića (1450-1950), Zagreb, Jugoslavenska Akademija znanosti i umjetnosti, 1950, p. 301-310; F. POSSET, *Marcus Marulus and the Biblia Latina of 1489. An approach to his biblical hermeneutics*, Cologne, Böhlau Verlag, 2013.

⁴ The *Davidiad*, preserved in autograph in: TURIN, Biblioteca nazionale, G.VI.40, has gone through eight modern editions. The *editio princeps* is M. MARULIĆ, *Davidias*,

edited by J. BADALIĆ, Zagreb, Jugoslavenska Akademija znanosti i umjetnosti, 1954; the most reliable and accessible editions are the latest two: M. MARULIĆ, *Davidijada*, edited and transl. by B. GLAVIČIĆ - B. LUČIN, Zagreb, Matica hrvatska, 2019 (Latin text and Croatian translation), and M. MARULIĆ, *The Davidiad*, edited and transl. by E. MULHOLLAND, Ghent, Lysa, 2024 (Latin text and English translation).

appendix to his will.⁵ The other list, *Inventarium librorum*, was composed by the executors of the will, soon after Marulić's death in 1524. The lists differ somewhat in the titles they itemize; close study of Marulić's works moreover reveals that during his life he also had books which are not mentioned in either list. But it is certain that his library contained more than 170 titles. The *Repertorium librorum* grouped them in *Ecclesiastici* and *Libri zentilium*, the latter group subdivided into *Poetae*, *Historici*, *Geographi*, *Grammatici*, *Commento*, *Epistolae*, *De re rustica*, *Astronomi*, *Philosophi et oratores*. Lexicographic works that Marulić possessed were recorded in the category *Grammatici*, which had thirteen entries (from the following I have omitted grammars in our modern sense and added numbering and bibliographic information):⁶

2. *Tortellius item Junianus* (the first title is Giovanni TORTELLI, *De orthographia dictionum e Graecis tractarum*, Vicenza, Stephan Koblinger, 1479, GW M47233; we can be sure because Marulić's copy, with marginal notes in his own hand, is preserved in Split, in the Dominican St. Catherine's Priory; the *Junianus* is Giuniano MAIO, *Liber de priscorum proprietate verborum*, first published Naples, Matthias of Olmütz and Biagio Romero, 1475, GW M20095).

3. *Cornu copiae* (Niccolò PEROTTI, *Cornucopiae*, first published Venice, Paganinus de Paganinis, 1489, GW M31093).

4. *Nonius Marcellus et Festus Pompeius* (an edition similar to Nonius MARCELLUS, *De proprietate sermonum*; SEXTUS POMPEIUS FESTUS, *De verborum significatu*; Marcus TERENTIUS VARRO, *De lingua latina*, Milan, Johannes Angelus Scinzenzeller, 1500, GW M27212).

5. *Jurisconsulti de verborum significatione* (an edition similar to Maffeo VEGIO, *De significatione verborum in iure civili*, Vicenza, Philippus Albinus, 1477, GW M49540).

⁵ Both lists in L. MARGETIĆ - B. LUČIN (edited by), *Marci Maruli testamentum*, in: «Colloquia Maruliana» XIV (2005), p. 25-71.

⁶ Identifications from B. LUČIN, *Jedan model humanističke recepcije klasične antike: «In epigrammata priscorum commentarius» Marka Marulića* (doctoral thesis), Zagreb, University of Zagreb, 2011 (includes the first complete edition of Marulić's text); ID., *Implicitni izvori*

u Marulićevevu Tumaču uz natpise starih: Niccolò Perotti, Pomponio Leto i drugi, in: «Colloquia Maruliana» XXI (2012), p. 143-183. For the incunables I supply also identifiers from the online database «Gesamtkatalog der Wiegendrucke» (GW). I have also tried to standardize Latin orthography of the citations throughout this paper as much as possible, preserving uncommon Renaissance spellings only when necessary.

6. *Laurentii Vallae Elegantiae* (Lorenzo VALLA, *Elegantiae linguae Latinae*, first published Brescia, Statius Gallicus, 1475, GW M49267).
8. *Eleganter dicta ex autoribus* (Albertus de EYB, *Margarita poetica [Oratorum omnium, poetarum, istoricorum ac philosophorum eleganter dicta]*, first published Nürnberg, Johann Sensenschmidt, 1472, GW 9529).
9. *Vocabula per ordinem collecta* (Dionysius NESTOR, *Vocabularium*, first published Milan, Leonardus Pachel and Uldericus Scinzenzeler, 1483, GW M25974).
10. *Compendium Elegantiarum Vallae* (BONUS ACCURSIUS, *Compendium elegantiarum Laurentii Vallae*, first published Milan, Philippus de Lavagna, 1475, GW 168).
11. *Vocabula de Graeco derivata* (cannot be identified).
12. *Varro De lingua Latina* (Marcus TERENCE VARRO, *De lingua latina. Analogia*, first published Rome, Georgius Lauer, c. 1471–72, GW M49457).

Bratislav Lučin remarks that, from Jean-Louis Charlet's representative list of humanist Latin lexicography presented in 2004–2005, Marulić was lacking only Calepino's *Dictionarium Latinum* (first edition: Venetiis, Dionisii Bertochi impressoris, 1502) and Crastone's *Lexicon Graeco-Latinum* (first edition: Venetiis, Aldus Manutius, 1497).⁷ Further sources of architectural vocabulary were titles from other groups in Marulić's library, such as *Historici*, which contained among the classical Latin titles Sabellico's *Rhapsodiae historiarum enneades ab orbe condito* (first edition: Venetiis, Bernardinus de Vitalibus et Matthaeus Venetus, 1498 [GW M39255]); we shall see below that the *Enneades* influenced Marulić's vocabulary); the group *Commento*, which listed Servius on Vergil and comments on Cicero; *De re rustica*, which included, besides Varro, Cato and Columella, the *Ruralia commoda* of Pietro de' Crescenzi in both Latin and Italian version; and also, as we shall see, from the group *Ecclesiastici* (especially *Biblia cum commento*) and the *Philosophi et oratores* (a PLINII *De naturali historia* which Marulić excerpted for his commonplace-book *Repertorium*;⁸ in the library he had a separate *Compendium* PLINII

⁷ B. LUČIN, *Jedan model*, cit., p. 104; J. L. CHARLET, *La lexicographie latine de l'époque humaniste*, in: «Acta classica Universitatis scientiarum Debrecensis» 40-41 (2004-2005), p. 401-427.

⁸ Marulić's autograph is in: ROME, Biblioteca nazionale centrale, ms. *Gesuitico* 522;

cf. *Repertorium* MARCI MARULI, edited by B. GLAVIČIĆ, 3 vol., Split, Književni krug, 1998-2000; analysis of sources D. NOVAKOVIĆ, *Zašto nam je važan Marulićev Repertorij?*, in: «Colloquia Maruliana» VII (1998), p. 9-24.

Naturalis historiae, perhaps put together by Marulić himself, which does not survive).

The library lists also suggest that lexicographical interests and strategies were nurtured in Marulić's family; these are attested by seven commonplace-books, today lost, prepared both by Marulić and by his father: *Compendium Bibliae per Marcum Marulum*, *Synonyma et epitheta et Valerii Maximi compendium per Marcum Marulum*, *Repertorium historiarum per alphabetum*, *Collibetus Nicolai Maruli patris*, *Collibetus Marci Maruli*, *Rhetoricae novae compendium*, *Collecta Nicolai Maruli patris*.

4. *Epistylia in the Temple of Jerusalem*

In the first of his religious successes, the *De institutione bene vivendi per exempla sanctorum*, in book 5, chapter 8, *De perseverantia bene agendi*, having presented examples of perseverance – first male, then female, first from the Bible, then from the lives of saints – Marulić concludes with an exhortation to the readers. In it, the author sees perseverance also in the form of physical objects from the Bible. Among the objects are the two columns from Solomon's Jerusalem Temple, and *epistylium* denotes a capital, the top section of the column:

Haec est ergo columna Iachin et columna Booz, id est, firmitatis et fortitudinis, quae epistylia liliorum malogranatorumque sustentant. Quia firmi ac fortis est summam conservare virtutum quam semel amplexus fuerit (Inst. 5, 8).⁹

The columns from the Temple receive similar interpretation also in Marulić's brief life of Solomon in the biographical compendium *De Veteris Instrumenti viris illustribus* (1517-1518, preserved in autograph, first published 1979; Marulić wrote *epistiliis* for *epistyliis*):

⁹ M. MARULIĆ, *Institucija / De institutione bene vivendi per exempla sanctorum*, edited and transl. by B. GLAVIČIĆ, vol. III, Split,

Književni krug Split, 1986-1987 ('Sabrana djela Marka Marulića' V), p. 484.

Salomon artificem regis Hiram accersivit de Tyro, qui ex aere duas fudit columnas cum epistiliis. Has posuit in porticu templi. Columnam dextram nuncupavit Iachin, id est firmitatem, laevam Booz, id est fortitudinem (Vir. ill. Salomon).¹⁰

Marulić's source for both passages is the Bible, II *Paralipomenon* 3-4 (in Marulić's Vulgate, *Regum* III). The Vulgate, which I will cite from Marulić's own copy, prefers the term *capitellum*, using *epistylum* outside the context of the two main columns:

Et porticum columnarum fecit quinquaginta cubitorum longitudinis et triginta cubitorum latitudinis: et alteram porticum in facie maioris porticus: et columnas et epistylia super columnas fecit. [...] et finxit duas columnas aereas decem et octo cubitorum altitudinis columnam unam: et linea duodecim cubitorum ambiebat columnam utramque. Duo quoque capitella fecit qui ponerentur supra capita columnarum fusilia ex aere quinque cubitorum altitudinis capitellum unum: et quinque cubitorum altitudinis capitellum alterum: et quasi in modum retis et cathenarum sibi inuicem miro opere contextarum. Utrumque capitellum columnarum fusile erat. Septena uersuum retiacula in capitello uno et septena retiacula in capitello altero. Et perfecit columnas et duos ordines per circuitum retiaculorum singulorum ut tegerent capitella quae erant super summitatem malogranatorum. Eodem modo fecit et capitello secundo. Capitella autem quae erant super capita columnarum quasi opere lilii fabricata erant in porticum quattuor cubitorum: et rursum alia capitella in summitate columnarum desuper iuxta mensura columnae contra retiacula. Malogranatorum autem ducenti ordines erant in circuitu capitelli secundi. Et statuit duas columnas in porticu templi. Cumque statuisset columnam dexteram: vocavit eam nomine Iachin. Similiter erexit columnam secundam: et vocavit nomen eius Booz. Et super capita columnarum opus in modum lilii posuit: perfectumque est opus columnarum.¹¹

Marulić's surviving copy of the Vulgate was listed in the *Repertorium librorum* as *Biblia cum commento*. It is the four-volume *Biblia Latina cum postillis* and includes the Postils (running Scripture commentaries) by Nicholas of Lyra (1270-1349). Lyra *ad locum* identifies *epistylia* as capitals: (f) *Et epistylia, id est capitella quae erant super columnas ad decorem*. He also explains the meaning of Hebrew names of the columns. In Marulić's

¹⁰ M. MARULIĆ, *Starozavjetne ličnosti / De Veteris Instrumenti viris illustribus commentarius*, edited and transl. by B. GLAVIČIĆ, Split, Književni krug Split, 1991 ('Sabrana djela Marka Marulića' VII), p. 88.

¹¹ *Biblia Latina cum postillis*, Venetiis, Bonetus Locatellus per Octavianum Scotum, vol. I, 1489, f. 257v-258r; Marulić's copy is in: SPLIT, Franciscan monastery of St. Anthony.

copy, the explanations are marked by two handwritten marginal notes: *Iachin. Booz*. This suggests that Marulić's attention lingered on the following lines of Lyra, from which Marulić will also take *firmitas* and *fortitudo* for his own writings:

(k) *Vocavit eam nomine Iachin, quod interpretatur firmitas. (l) Similiter erexit columnam secundam, scilicet in sinistra parte. (m) Et vocavit nomen eius Booz, quod interpretatur fortitudo. Et dicunt Hebraei quod per istas duas columnas signabatur firmitas et robur regni David. Cetera patent ex dictis.*

When Marulić chose to use *epistylum* and not *capitellum* for the top sections of the two main columns, he moved away from the biblical text. For the interpretation he relied on Lyra, but Lyra used the term *capitellum* throughout his long discussion of the two columns. I see Marulić's choice as a humanist contribution, a refined use of Latin vocabulary.

At the same time, this is a choice that Marulić could have noted in another book in his library, in Sabellico's *Enneades*. In Book 9 of the first *Ennead* Sabellico also describes the Temple:

*Statuit et columnas duas aeneas ante vestibulum duodevicenum cubitum celsitudine, ambituque duodenum: epistilia fusilia inque liliorum speciem figurata.*¹²

The views of humanist lexicographers, relying on Vitruvius, were wider. Tortelli in the *De orthographia* writes that *epistylum* can mean both "a small column" and "a capital":

*Epistylon cum t exili sequente y Graeco: et penultima cum unico l et i latino scribitur: traducitur ab aliquibus columnella: ita ut sit diminutivum styli: quae est columna. Alii etiam capitellum, quod supra stylon ponitur, intelligi voluerunt.*¹³

Tortelli follows ISID., *orig.*, 15, 8: «*Epistolia sunt quae super capitella columnarum ponuntur*»,¹⁴ although introducing a variant of the word. In his copy of Tortelli, Marulić left an annotation at the margin of the entry *epistylon*, where he wrote *columna*. But he chose to disregard this

¹² MARCI ANTONII SABELLICI *Enneades*, Venetiis, Bernardinus de Vitalibus et Matthaeus Venetus, 1498 (GW M39255), f. LVv.

¹³ G. TORTELLI, *De orthographia*, f. [152v]. For Marulić's copy in Split, see above.

¹⁴ Marulić had *Ethimologiae Isidori* in his library too: «*Marci Maruli testamentum*», p. 66.

sense when he was writing the *De institutione* (in 1496-1499), and to disregard the spelling in the *De viris illustribus* (1517-1518). On the latter occasion he preferred – *pace* Tortelli, the Bible and Lyra – the way the word was printed in Sabellico's *Enneades*.

The spelling *epistilium* is used by Giuniano Maio, for whom the word denotes architrave, the lintel or beam that rests on the capitals of columns. This meaning differs from the one in Lyra and Tortelli. The expanded later edition of Maio, printed in Venice 1482 (we cannot be sure that Marulić used Maio in that edition; I cite it because it is the one with most copies surviving today), adds information from Tortelli and suggests that the difference in spellings reflects a difference in meanings:

Epistilium trabs quae super columnas ponitur.

*Epistylum uel columnella diminutiuum a styli: uel capitellum quod supra stylium. T.*¹⁵

For the first definition, Maio relied on Pompeius Festus. In *De verborum significatu* in the Rome, 1471-1472 edition, the text reads: «*Epistilium trabs: quae super columnas ponitur*».¹⁶

In Marulić's works, the sense of *epistylum* is restricted to the top section of a column. This meaning comes from biblical sources: the Vulgate, the commentary of Nicolaus de Lyra, the biblical paraphrasis in Sabellico's *Enneades*. Marulić's autograph annotations in his copy of Tortelli testify that at one time the author from Split must have been aware of other senses of *epistylum*, the senses given by a number of dictionaries and thesauri in his library (Isidore, Festus, Tortelli, Maio).

Marulić's awareness of the lexical senses of *epistylum* must have been influenced by the context: in the *De institutione* and the *De Veteris Instrumenti viris illustribus* Marulić was writing on a Christian and biblical subject, therefore *epistylum* meant what he had learned from the description of Solomon's Temple. But Marulić's humanist reflexes were nevertheless active: contrary to his biblical sources, he chose a refined, less frequent Grecism *epistylum* over the more common Latin *capitellum*.

¹⁵ IUNIANI MAII *Liber de priscorum proprietate verborum*, Venetiis, Octavianus Scotus, 1482 (GW M20104) [s.v.].

¹⁶ NONII MARCELLI *De proprietate*, Remember that Marulić had a similar edition [s.v.].

5. *A palace in the Davidiad*

In the *Davidiad* Marulić was turning the biblical story about the King David into fourteen cantos of epic Latin verse followed by a separate tropological commentary. The short notice in 2 *Samuel* 5: 11 «Now Hiram king of Tyre sent envoys to David, along with cedar logs and carpenters and stonemasons, and they built a palace for David» inspired the poet to compose a vivid description of the building process and the palace itself, comprising some sixty verses (*Dav.*, 8, 12-69). Marulić's *demonstratio* starts with laying foundations and raising walls, beams, ceilings and roofs with a water-cachment system; it moves to depicting the atria, arches, the dome, the mosaics in the portico, the doors and numerous other parts of the house; it ends with an ekphrasis of paintings and statues which adorn the palace. A remarkable poetic effect is achieved by embedding in verse carefully chosen architectural vocabulary. The hexameters interweave both more common terms (such as *domus, saxa, area, murus*) and the more technical ones (*cementa, malta, laquearia, imbrices, impluvium*).

Here I concentrate on several architectural terms from two sections of the passage. The first section describes the atria, the portico and its decorations:

*Atria marmoreae circumdant lata columnae,
quas superiniecti presserunt fornicis arcus.
Stat testudinea subter cava porticus umbra,
hic asarota nitent variis distincta figuris
picturasque suas paries crustatus ophite
et Phrygio et Parii monstrat candore lapilli.*
(*Dav.*, 8, 20-25)

The other section is an *enumeratio* of the parts of the palace, ending in a hyperbolic final of the uncountable and unutterable:

*Acceptit reliquas tandem nova regia partes:
andron et exedras, gynecia, septa, dietas
erectosque gradus, diversa cubicula, longe
lateque effusas aulas crebrasque fenestras
clatratas ferro quasdam, quasdamque patentes
cum podiis. Numerare grave est illa omnia, nedum
enarrare decus rerumque exponere formas.*
(*Dav.*, 8, 35-41)

6. *Testudineus in a shaded dome*

The *Oxford Latin Dictionary* defines *testudineus* as «1 Characteristic of a tortoise. 2 Made of, or overlaid with, tortoise-shell». Neither meaning quite fits Marulić's *testudinea umbra* (*Dav.*, 8, 22; Mulholland translates the verse «Below's a portico with shaded dome»).¹⁷ For Marulić *testudineus* here meant «shaped like a tortoise-shell». In this he followed Isidore's explanation of *testudo*, *orig.*, 15, 8, 5 (note how Isidore connects *testudo* with *atrium*):

Testudo est camera templi obliqua. Nam in modum testudinis veteres templorum tecta faciebant; quae ideo sic fiebant ut caeli imaginem redderet, quod constat esse convexum. Alii testudinem volunt esse locum in parte atrii adversum venientibus.

An interpretation of *testudineus* along similar lines was given in *Cornucopiae*: «*Hinc etiam concamerata loca dicimus testudinea, hoc est quae fornicibus constant*» (I, 2, 190).¹⁸ *Testudinea umbra* is thus Marulić's poetic *callida iunctura* developed on the basis of ancient and Neo-Latin lexicography.

7. *Asarotum, crustatus, ophites in a mosaic*

Architecture and parts of the house are prominent themes in *Cornucopiae* I, 2, 178-204.¹⁹ On these pages Perotti explains, beside *testudineus*, a number of further terms that Marulić used in the description of David's palace. The first such term is *asarota*: «*Inuenta deinde sunt a Graecis elaborata arte picturae quae asarota dicta sunt, quod uerri non debeant, ἀπὸ τοῦ α (priuatiua particula est), et σαρῶ quod est uerro*» (I, 2, 187). A little further Perotti cites *STAT., silv.*, 1, 3, 53-56: «*Hoc pauimenti genus laudat Papinius in uilla Tyburtina Manlii Vopisci: "Calcabam nec opimus opes, nam splendor ab alto Defluus et nitidum referentes aera testae,*

¹⁷ M. MARULIĆ, *The Davidiad*, cit., p. 275.

¹⁸ NICOLAI PEROTTI *Cornu copiae seu linguae Latinae commentarii*, edited by

J. L. CHARLET, Sassoferrato, Istituto internazionale di studi piceni, 1991, vol. II, p. 79.

¹⁹ *Ibid.*, p. 74-79.

Monstrauere solum, uarias ubi picta per artes Gaudet humus superat que nouis asarota figuris». The co-occurrence *uarias... asarota figuris* in Statius's description inspired Dav., 8, 23: «*hic asarota nitent variis distincta figuris*» (and later *picturasque* probably reflects Statius's *picta*).

In *Cornucopiae* I, 7, 10 the word *crusta* will be defined as «*Crusta enim feminino genere fragmentum tenue significat lapidis aut ligni aut uitri aut gelu aut alterius huiusmodi*». ²⁰ The word appeared already twice in I, 2, 189: «*Lithostratum uocant quale Praeneste fuisse in Fortunae delubro memoratur. Paruulis id crustis constat, ideo que lithostratum appellatur*» and then immediately after the *concamerata loca*: «*Huiusmodi pauimenta lapideis siue figulinis crustis constant uitro tectis atque encausto pictis*».

Perotti, however, is not Marulić's most probable immediate source for *paries crustatus ophite* in Dav., 8, 24. As reported by the *apparatus locorum* in Mulholland's edition, *paries crustatus* is verbally closer to SIDON., *carm.*, 22 (*Burgus Pontii Leontii*), 146-147: «*sectilibus paries tabulis crustatus ad aurea / tecta venit*». The link of *crustatus* and *paries* could have been strengthened in Marulić's mind also by what he had found in ISID., *orig.*, 19, 13: «*Crustae autem sunt tabulae marmoris. Unde et marmorati parietes et crustati dicuntur*». ²¹ Nevertheless, Perotti's remarks must have helped Marulić's understanding of *crustatus* and related words as connected with mosaics, and must have made the poet's assimilation of vocabulary easier.

Marulić imagines the wall of David's palace embellished with mosaic made of three kinds of marble: ophite, Phrygian and Parian stone. *Ophites* is in the *Vocabularium* of Dionysius Nestor:

Ophis cum ph et in Latino serpens interpretatur, a quo ophites, marmoris genus, serpentinae maculas detinentis, dictus est teste Plinio lib. XXXVI naturalis histo. et producit phi syllabam. Statius lib. silvarum primo: Maeret onyx longe queriturque exclusus ophites. Lucanus lib. IX: Quam parvis tinctus maculis thebanus ophites. ²²

²⁰ NICOLAI PEROTTI *Cornu copiae seu linguae Latinae commentarii*, edited by J. L. CHARLET, vol. V, Sassoferato, Istituto internazionale di studi piceni, 1995, p. 10.

²¹ ISIDORI HISPALENSIS *Etymologiae. De summo bono*, Venetiis, Bonetus Locatel-

lus per Octavianum Scotum, 1493 (GW M15267), f. 70v.

²² DIONYSII NESTORIS *Vocabularium*, Venetiis, Philippus Pincius, 1496 (GW M25986), f. LXXIIIr.

Tortelli's *De orthographia* repeats the information on spelling, but cites Pliny *verbatim* and omits Statius and Lucanus: «*Ophites cum i Latino et t exili scribitur; est teste Pli. in XXXVI natura. histo. genus marmoris maculas serpentinas detinentis; a quibus nomen ipsum assumpsit*»; Marulić annotated Tortelli's entry with a marginal note *marmor*. In 1516, in the prologue of the *Evangelistarium*, the author from Split chose to bring up ophite as the most precious kind of marble:

*Quemadmodum inter marmora ophites, inter gemmas adamas, inter metalla aurum aestimatione pretioque praestare putantur...*²³

Dav., 8, 25 ends in a memorable clausula *candore lapilli*. The collocation has a classical source: CURT., 9, 1, 4, a description of the Indian king Sophites surrendering to Alexander the Great (Marulić possessed the Venice 1498 edition,²⁴ listed in the will as *Quintus Curtius et Polibius, volumen unum*). Curtius was quoted in Valla's *Elegantiae*, Book VI, in the last chapter (*Gemmae lapilli*), to prove that the words from the title of the chapter can be synonyms:

*Curtius li. VIII. cum dixisset gemmas margaritasque mare littoribus infundit, paulo post de eisdem Indis ait: Lapilli ex auribus pendent: profecto perlucidi intelligendi sunt, et iterum li. X. de rege Indo: pendebant ex auribus insignes candore ac magnitudine lapilli.*²⁵

The notion and citations from Curtius were also taken up by Perotti (I, 1, 403). But Marulić's clausula is closer to the paraphrasis of Curtius in Sabellico's *Enneades* IV, 6:

*Erat illi vestis auro et purpura distincta: aureis soleis inseruerat gemmas: brachia et lacerti margaritis nitebant: ex auribus insigni candore lapilli suspensi.*²⁶

And yet, contrary to Curtius, Sabellico's *Enneades*, the *Cornucopiae* and Valla, in *Dav.*, 8, 25 Marulić does not intend to say that the walls

²³ M. MARULIĆ, *Evangelistar / Euangelistarium*, edited and transl. by B. GLAVIČIĆ, Split, Književni krug Split, 1985 ('Sabrana djela Marka Marulića' IV), vol. I, p. 422.

²⁴ D. NOVAKOVIĆ, *Zašto nam je*, cit., p. 20.

²⁵ LAURENTII VALLAE *Elegantiae linguae Latinae*, Brescia, Statius Gallicus, 1475 (GW M49267).

²⁶ MARCI ANTONII SABELLICI *Enneades*, cit., f. CCXXIXv.

were decorated with gems. Here we see the poet at work; his (auditory) memory noted the co-occurrence *candore lapilli*, but his imagination placed *lapillus* in the context of mosaics – it gave the word its proper, not metaphorical sense.

8. *Ferro clatrata fenestra*

Marulić's list of parts of the palace ends with windows (*Dav.*, 8, 38-41). Some of them are set with bars of iron, *ferro clatratae*.²⁷ Both *clatratus* and its verb, *clatro*, are rare in classical Latin; in the *Thesaurus linguae Latinae*, the article for *clatro* (which includes the participle) is ten lines long and cites six attestations. As we will see, although neither *clatri* nor *clatratus* appears in Festus, Perotti, Tortelli, Nestor, or Giuniano Maio, *clatratus* was not so uncommon in Renaissance Latin; it was to be found in commentaries.

Marulić, whose will lists a *Virgilius cum comento* and a (Servius) *super Aeneidam*, could first have encountered *clatrata* in the context of *fenestra* in Servius's commentary of a difficult line in the *Aeneid* – 3, 152: «*plena per insertas fundebat luna fenestras*»:

*Insertas: aut clatratas, aut non seratas: ut sit quasi inseratas, id est non clausas: et est dictum quomodo asprosque molares per asperos, compostus per compositus, vixet pro vixisset.*²⁸

Servius's focus is elsewhere and he does not say what *clatratus* exactly means. The sense of the word is provided by a commentary on Columella.

The exact edition behind Marulić's «*Collumella cum quibusdam aliis*» cannot be identified with certainty, but the wording suggests that this could have been the one printed in Bologna in 1504, with a commentary

²⁷ Marulić appreciated the collocation *ferro clatrata fenestra* enough to use it once again in the *Davidiad*, describing the house arrest of David's concubines raped by his rebellious son Absalom: «*nulli aditus patuit. Ferro clatrata fenestra / pro-*

spectum tribuit vitaeque alimenta recepit» (*Dav.*, 12, 177-178).

²⁸ PUBLII VERGILII MARONIS *Opera*, Venetiis [Baptista de Tortis, c. 1482]; GW M49792, p. [227].

of Filippo Beroaldo the Elder. There Beroaldo comments *clatri* twice (at COLUM., 6, 37, 10 and 8, 3, 3) in a very similar way:

*Clatris munitus: Clatros uocant ligna transversaria quales sunt cancelli, quibus fenestrae mutuuntur(!): unde clatratae nominantur. Cato Portius: bubilia bona praesepes clatratas. Clatros oportet inter se pede distare.*²⁹

*Clatris muniantur: Clatri sunt ligna transversa quibus aliquid munitur, a quibus fenestrae clatratae dicuntur; cancelli quoque nominantur. Oratius: obiectos caveae ualuit si frangere clatros. Cato: clatros inter se oportet pede distare.*³⁰

The exact phrase *clatrata fenestra* was used once in Latin literature, PLAUT., *Mil.*, 379: «*neque fenestra nisi clatrata*». The passage was explained at length in the commented edition prepared by Giovanni Battista Pio (Bologna, 1468-1543), printed in Milan in 1500. Pio brings together attestations from Propertius, Servius (whose *serratas* Pio corrects into *clatratas*), Cato and Columella; Pio also states explicitly that the bars on the window are made of iron (*cancellis ferreis*). I cite only the first, most relevant part of Pio's note:

*Clatrata fenestra. Clatrata: cancellata: ferrea: cancellis ferreis cancellatim plagosa instar maculosi retis. Clatros appellamus ligna transuersaria: dicimus et Clatra. Propertius libro elegiaco quarto: Et canis in nostros nimis experrecta dolores / Cum fallenda meo pollice clatra forent. Mendum est in codice Seruiano: ubi ita ante nos legebatur: plena per insertas fundebat luna phenestras: subdit Seruius: Insertas aut caelatas aut non serratas. Tu scribe ex antiquis exemplaribus: aut non clatratas.*³¹

Marulić mentions Plautus several times, writing once even *in Plauto legimus*,³² but we do not know whether he used one of the editions with

²⁹ *Opera agricolationum, COLUMELLAE, VARRONIS, CATONISQUE, nec non PALLADII, cum annotationibus d. PHILIPPI BEROALDI, Bononiae, Benedictus Hector Bononiensis, 1504, f. 93v.*

³⁰ *Ibid.*, f. 108r.

³¹ PLAUTUS *integer cum interpretatione* IOAN-NIS BAPTISTAE PIJ, Mediolani, Ulrich Scinzenzeller, 1500 (GW M33974), f. [227v].

³² M. MARULIĆ, *In epigrammata prisorum commentarius* 6, 1: «*Nam in Plauto legimus: 'Libet etiam Carinum quid agat obseruare, nouum nuptum'*» (PLAUT., *Cas.*, 859). B. LUČIN, *Jedan model*, cit., p. 123 shows that Marulić here cites (without naming the source) Perotti's *Cornucopiae* 39, 3, 6-8.

Pio's comments. The case of *ferro clatrata fenestra*, however, reveals limitations of Renaissance lexicography: a word and a phrase were missing in the major lexicographic works. Here the commentaries must have given assistance, providing descriptions and analyses of lexical relationships, and thus fulfilling the same needs as lexicons.

9. Conclusion

The example of Marko Marulić from Split, a representative Renaissance humanist about whom we know a lot, shows that he intensively used the lexicographic works in his library (Festus, Isidore, Perotti, Tortelli, Giuniano Maio, Dionysius Nestor, Valla). Marulić's main concern was religion, and that made him narrow down the range of available meanings of a Latin word (the case of *epistylum*). Ancient and Renaissance lexicography, on the other hand, led Marulić to use words differently than we would expect on the basis of modern dictionaries (*testudineus*) and offered him clusters of semantically related terms and phrases (*asarotum*, *paries crustatus*, *ophites*). The lexicography, in large measure derivative, had its limitations, missing repeatedly certain words and phrases (*clatrata fenestra*); in such cases the humanists would find help in commentaries of classical texts.